

**ON SOME FEATURES OF THE CULINARY VOCABULARY OF THE UZBEK
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the history and current state of Uzbek culinary vocabulary. The article also analyzes mutual terms that relate to Arabic, Tajik and Russian-international lexemes. At the end of the article, it is recommended to use these terms when specifying industry terminology.

Key words: vocabulary, cooking, subsystem, poetic works, food, confectionery, culinary vocabulary, culinary terminology, khalisa, cake.

The high culture of the Central Asian peoples has been known since ancient times. Archaeological excavations indicate that civilization existed here several millennia BC. It must be emphasized that even in primitive society people were engaged in cattle breeding, fishing, animal husbandry, and also agriculture. At a later time, our ancestors knew how to process iron, copper and other metals, made various tools from them, built boats, weaving, etc.

During this era, vocabulary began to form in the language of our ancestors, denoting persons engaged in these crafts. Evidence of this is the names of specialties recorded in the Orkhon-Yenisei written monuments: baduzchi (wood and bone carver), yerchi (guide, guide), etc.

Professional terms covering all aspects of cooking have a centuries-old history in Central Asia and, in particular, in Uzbekistan. They are firmly connected with the characteristics of the social, everyday and cultural life of the people. Uzbek linguistics has experience in writing monographic studies on professional vocabulary - these are the works of N. Mamaatov, S. Ibrokhimov, N. Ikramov, R. Daniyarov, and others.

In the Uzbek language, the word “pazandachilik” (cooking) denotes all areas associated with baking flatbreads, cooking bekmes (grape molasses), halva, nishallo (a delicacy made from sugar and whipped egg whites) and other dishes. Each master, even if he performs a separate work process or prepares a single dish, is called by a name related to a particular branch (profession) nonvoy, halvogar, etc. Terms related to one or another area of life are closely related to the socio-historical and everyday features of the life of the people. It should be emphasized that the topic of our work, by its nature, is not confined to the framework of linguistics, and this prompted us to turn

Culinary vocabulary, which has a long history, is one of the important components of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. It occupies its special place in two subsystems of vocabulary: 1) in the subsystem of everyday vocabulary; 2) in the subsystem of professional-industrial vocabulary, which, in turn, occupy their necessary place in the general lexical system of the Tajik language.

Despite some lexical, morphological and phonetic differences in dialects, the bulk of culinary terms are common to all regions of the republic.

On the other hand, some of this vocabulary is widely used in the general Tajik language, while others are known only in certain professional areas. At the same time, narrowly professional terms are partially connected and intertwined with dialectal ones.

The linguistic basis for studying the culinary vocabulary of the Uzbek language and the history of its development are: pre-revolutionary book sources, special treatises on culinary recipes, traditional culinary canons - dasturs, explanatory dictionaries, poetic works. We did not find any special dictionaries of culinary vocabulary. Part of the vocabulary contained in these sources continues to exist in the modern Uzbek language and its dialects, the other part is not common in the modern Uzbek language and is specific to this group of sources.

Another group consists of modern Uzbek culinary vocabulary, both national and dialectal, which is increasingly penetrating all types and genres of Uzbek literature, including scientific literature.

There is a close relationship between these two groups of sources. The difference lies only in the degree of familiarity and mastery of them in modern conditions.

If in ancient times the rich assortment of Uzbek cuisine existed for a limited circle of the ruling elite and specialists, and only a small part of it was available to the broad masses of the people, then now, under the conditions of an independent system, the variety of food dishes and culinary products is becoming one of the most striking manifestations improving the well-being of the Uzbek peoples. This explains the revival of Uzbek cooking, and with it the intensive development of culinary terminology on the basis of literary, book and colloquial dialectal vocabulary, as well as through the enrichment of borrowed vocabulary from the languages of the peoples of the CIS and foreign countries. Currently, the international layer of Uzbek culinary vocabulary makes up a significant part of it, and it is constantly developing and enriching.

The old culinary craft is increasingly turning into an art, and the names of products play an important role in this art.

The culinary terms and names we have collected can help in finding or creating semantically, phonetically and aesthetically appropriate names for various types of rapidly developing Uzbek cuisine, especially in the field of baking and confectionery, the products of

which are highly appreciated at national and international exhibitions.

For further research of the culinary vocabulary of the Uzbek language, it is necessary, first of all, to lexicographically process it and compile the most complete explanatory and bilingual dictionary of culinary vocabulary from all available sources. At the same time, based on the specifics of this area of terminology, it is necessary to explain in sufficient detail not only the general meaning of the terms and names, but also the actions, objects and types of products they denote, indicating, where possible, all their components and their relationship, the method of preparation, purpose (general therapeutic and dietary nutrition, recommendations for certain diseases, etc.).

Thus, a dictionary of culinary vocabulary should be intended not only for linguists, but also for specialists in various fields (ethnographers and historians, botanists, biologists, nutritionists, etc.); as well as for a wide range of readers. Therefore, this dictionary should be of a mixed explanatory-encyclopedic type.

Studying the professional culinary vocabulary of the Uzbek language has theoretical and practical significance. The rich material collected in the process of studying culinary vocabulary and the analysis carried out can serve to develop the corresponding section of the lexicology of the Uzbek language (in the historical aspect). Determining the principles for creating culinary terms and names, their morphological and semantic features can be used to systematize and unify the necessary part of culinary terminology. In the process of the formation and development of individual layers of vocabulary, the proportion of the main ways of replenishing the vocabulary changed, among which the main and most intensive at all stages of the history of the Uzbek language were internal word formation and the borrowing of foreign language vocabulary.

Of all the languages from which borrowings enter the Uzbek language, Arabic is in first place. The reason for this is not only the Arab invasion, Islam and economic, political and cultural ties between Uzbeks and Arabs, but also the centuries-old orientation towards the Arabic language, strong Arabic-language trends until the beginning of the 20th century.

All this could not but affect the vocabulary of the Uzbek language, in particular, the culinary vocabulary, as a result of which many culinary terms appeared. Among them there are many that were formed from Arabic words or with their help. For example, *khalisa* (a dish made from wheat, meat and fat), *Rohatul-Khulkum* (Turkish Delight) “a delight for the throat.”

The centuries-old proximity of Tajiks and Uzbeks left a certain imprint on the language of both peoples and, above all, on the vocabulary. The geographical environment, economic development, cultural and everyday ties of both peoples constantly serve as the basis for the mutual use of words and terms. Therefore, Uzbek words and terms are included in the Tajik language and vice versa, and over time they become components of the culinary vocabulary of

both languages. Some of the Tajik terms in this industry are originally Uzbek or formed with the participation of Uzbek words. For example, kovurma shurva, kovurma palov, katlama, katik, kurtoba, kayla and others.

Russian-international terms are widely used in culinary vocabulary. Some of them came through spoken language, and some through various types of literature. For example, borscht, tobacco, compote, cake, salad, pies, marmalade and others.

Culinary vocabulary, which has a centuries-old history, is one of the important main parts of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language.

The results of the study can be used to highlight individual issues related to the economy, household, life and culture of the Uzbek people, as well as serve as the basis for specifying and supplementing the lexical part of the Uzbek language curriculum in schools and universities.

References:

1. Bobokalonov, O. Fayzullayev O. Psycholinguistique, synthèse entre les méthodes de la linguistique et celles de la psychologie. *Психология, илимий журнал*, 86-89.
2. Hojiyev A. Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati. -T.:2002. -168 b.
3. Hojiyev A. O'zbek tili sinonimlarining izohli lug'ati. -T.: 1974. -308 b.
4. Hojiyeva, G. S. "San'at" Terminining Fransuz Va O 'zbek Tili Lug 'Atlari Asosida Lingvo-Madaniy Tahlili. Qiyosiy Adabiyotshunoslik, Chog 'Ishtirma Tilshunoslik Va Tarjimashunoslik: Muammo, Yechim Va Istiqbollar. Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman. Buxoro, 2021.–B. 62-68.
5. Ikramova N. Uzbekskaya kulinarnaya leksika: Dis. ... kand. filol. nauk. – Tashkent, 1983. – 168 s.
6. Islomov, D. S. (2023). THE DIFFERENTIATION ASPECTS OF UZBEK AND FRENCH PHONETICS. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(11), 47-51.
7. Khamidova, M. K. (2021). The structure and means of expression of metaphorical units with deopoetonymy in french and uzbek languages. *Scientific reports of Bukhara state university*, 5(2), 67-83.
8. Muhammadovna, J. M. (2023). MATBUOT VA IJTIMOYIY NUTQ.
9. Narzullayeva, D. (2023). VOCABULARY OF THE QUR'AN IN THE OBJECT OF THEOLINGUISTICS. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 35(35).
10. Nasimova, F. (2023). FRANSUZ TILIDA ZONIMLAR BILAN IFODALANGAN FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING GRAMMATIK O'ZIGA XOSLIGI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 44(44).
11. Nasimova, F. (2023). FRANSUZ TILI TERMINOLOGIYASINING ONOMASTIK XUSUSIYATLARI TO'G'RISIDA. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 44(44).
12. Nasimova, F. (2023). FRANSUZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA INTONATSIYANING USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 42(42).
13. Nasimova, F. (2023). TERMIN VA UNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 42(42).
14. Nasimova, F. (2023). O 'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDA BO 'G 'IN TUZILISHI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 44(44).